
ПОЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3763157>

УДК 32.019.5

Do Ngoc Hanh

Do Ngoc Hanh, Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Lecturer, Deputy Dean, Faculty of Philosophy, Political University, Ministry of Defense, Hanoi, Vietnam. E-mail: dohanh2402hvct@mail.ru.

Features of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style and strengthen Vietnam – Russia comprehensive strategic partnership

Abstract. In the article, the author focuses on analyzing the features of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style on its 5 aspects: the truthfulness, the kindness and the beauty; wise diplomatic intelligence, independent, autonomy and creativity; cultural diplomacy; diplomatic conduct; the principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» and the art of «mindfulness». Thereby, the article continues to affirm the great merits and great contributions of President Ho Chi Minh to the Vietnamese diplomacy and revolutionary career, which is a clear demonstration of diplomatic style, scientific thinking, sharp political visions, the falling of one leaf heralds the autumn and the skill of «conquering people's hearts». This is a scientific basis for foreign policy, especially in order to strengthen the comprehensive strategic partnership between Vietnam and Russia and to celebrate the 70th anniversary of establishing diplomatic relations between the two peoples in the context of globalization.

Key words: diplomatic culture, Ho Chi Minh, strategic partnership, Vietnam - Russia, political culture.

Ho Chi Minh was known as a Vietnamese hero of national liberation, a great man of culture, a diplomat, and a talented architect, who founded modern Vietnamese diplomacy. The diplomatic approach is a cultural activity. Specifically, Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style represents the Vietnamese culture in the cultural exchange with the other nations. Thanks to this diplomatic style, Ho Chi Minh, who is an eminent culturalist and diplomat, showed his revolutionary and progressive goal because this diplomatic style includes the universal cultural values of humanity. The study of the authors Song Thanh, Duong Trung Quoc, Duong Quoc Thanh and Vo Van Sung says «Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style has been

identified as a diplomatic performance that reaches a cultural level, a way of thinking, rich culturally diplomatic conduct, is a human philosophy» [12, p. 12].

In order to formulate the concept of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style, it is necessary to clearly understand that his diplomatic way is not only the behaviors, the tactful methods and the art of diplomacy but also the ideologies and the diplomatic knowledge that he accumulated in the revolutionary struggle to shape his worldview and human outlook. First of all, Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style is manifested in a unity, in which heart (thinking) - action (actions) - speech (word) operate on the same axis of value which includes truth, kindness and beauty [15, p. 46].

Additionally, Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style represents the crystallization of great cultural values, national traditional diplomacy, cultural quintessence and worldwide diplomatic experience, which is embodied in ideologies, diplomatic art. This crystallization ensures sustainability, forever leads the way and become a guide to the development of Vietnamese diplomacy; demonstrates convincingly deep political thinking and the falling of one leaf heralds the autumn.

1. Noteworthy feature of truth - kindness - beauty of diplomacy

Truth, kindness, and beauty are the most common and eternal values, which symbolize the useful things and create perfection for human life and human society. Ingeniously, the truth, the kindness and the beauty are also the core content throughout Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture. The values of the truth, the kindness and the beauty in Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture influence the evaluation, sentiment and attitude of many leaders, politicians and people all over the world about Ho Chi Minh and Vietnam. Because of these values, Ho Chi Minh may be considered a longtime enemy of the opposition in terms of political stance, however he is forever praised by mankind as the «saint», one of the most honorable persons. «Truth» in Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture is understood in the sense of truthfulness and sincerity - as opposed to the false, the reluctance. When discussing the true value in Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture, it is unforgettable to mention sincerity. All actions and behaviors of Ho Chi Minh frequently come from conscience, right and the attitude that is very sincere, honest with people and with work. N.S Khrushchev, the First Secretary of the Soviet Communist Party recounted the first impression in a meeting with Ho Chi Minh when he made a diplomatic visit to Soviet union in 1950: «Ho Chi Minh was a true saint of the revolution. In his sightseeing, I can hardly forget that pure and sincere light. That is the sincerity of a steadfast communist and the purity of a person who completely sacrificed his life for his cause in principle and in action» [3, p.58]. His sincerity nurtured the sentiment and the respect of

others. When talking about Ho Chi Minh, W.Shaw - an American pilot could not control his emotions and had to say: Ho Chi Minh – «it was a fairy in Asian myth» [5, p. 19].

«The kindness» is inherently the best morality of human. The kindness and the good deeds coexist in Ho Chi Minh. Ho Chi Minh's most concentrated manifestation of kindness is, altruistic sentiment, kindness, love for people. He believed that «kindness is to properly implement the Communist Party's policies, to meet the obligations of most people (workers and farmers), to practice being truly hardworking, thrifty, honest, righteous and impartial, to benefit the revolution and the people on priority, on the contrary, it is evil» [9, p. 113]. Therefore, in his whole life, he persisted with the goal of fighting for national independence, people's happiness and peace for all humanity. This is Ho Chi Minh's desire and choice which he never changed. After all, this political goal is the cultural goal, crystallization of cultural values, the most noble thing. As a result, he advocated for the kindness in order to win, to convert, to deal with people: «Every human being has kindness and evil in his heart. We must know how to make the kindness parts of each person blossom like spring flowers and the bad ones fade away» [10, p. 672].

Firstly, «the beauty» must be true and kind. The truth, the kindness, and the beauty lead to special values and noble appearance of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture. The unity of the truth, the kindness and the beauty in Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style is clearly reflected in Ho Chi Minh's thought about the proletarian international spirit which focuses on establishing friendship and cooperation among nations so as to achieve the aim of peace, development and prosperity. The pure international spirit is the morality of diplomat Ho Chi Minh and closely attached even to his true patriotism. He desired the independence and freedom of his nation and respected the independence and freedom of other nations. His concept was that supporting other nations could protect his nation. It was a carefree, enthusiastic and

meaningful support for fostering solidarity. He was heartbroken when the fraternal parties were in disagreement. When the death was near, he did not forget to say the desire to «rationally rebuild solidarity between brother parties based on Marxism - Leninism and the proletarian internationalism» [10, p. 623]. Ho Chi Minh's point of view partly demonstrates the unity between the values of the truth, the kindness and the beauty in his diplomatic culture.

2. Noteworthy feature in the erudite diplomatic wisdom and independent skill and spirit, autonomy and creativity

Ho Chi Minh left a mark in the history of national diplomacy by the erudite wisdom and an independent, autonomous and creative skill and spirit. Because of the broad and conceptual understanding, creative thinking and superior vision, he created a unique and special diplomacy to successfully solve national practical problems. He deeply understood of motto of the Five senses has been summarized by the East to operate smoothly in foreign affairs: the five knowing - knowing oneself, knowing people, knowing the times, knowing and turning variables. Based on patriotism, the will of national liberation and practical research, Ho Chi Minh was precisely aware of the era trends to choose the right path. He determined to seek international support for the revolutionary career of his nation. This expressed the combination of national strength and the power of the intellectual age of Ho Chi Minh. Because of the progressive vision, overcoming the limitations of its predecessors, Ho Chi Minh contributed greatly to changing national consciousness and national destiny.

Diplomatic intelligence Ho Chi Minh also manifests in analyzing and handling conflicts that arised in the diplomatic process. After having imbued Marxist-Leninist theory, Ho Chi Minh said: «Everything is contradictory», «the contradiction is available in everything» [13, p. 52]. More specifically, in order to resolve conflicts, Ho Chi Minh proactively and patiently exploits each positive similarity even the smallest as a basis, suspending the differences or trying to

handle discernible differences to talk together. He is a diplomat with a knack for negotiating, always looking for common ground in every conversation to come to the most positive deal. He effectively applied the thought V.I. Lenin: «It is only possible to win against a stronger enemy with a great effort, and under a mandatory condition we must know how to take advantage of it very meticulously, very attentively, very carefully, very wisely for the smallest «cracks» of interests among enemies» [4, p. 68].

Ho Chi Minh is always proactive in conduct whether the interlocutor is the president, leader of the Communist Party, politician, intellectual or ordinary people. That initiative is both natural, simple, sincere, and considerate and sensitive, expressed in a very lively and plentiful manner. Due to his subtlety and agility, he is able to take the initiative and turn around the situation when it is necessary to achieve his external goals. General Secretary of the Communist Party of England, John Gollan expressed: «Meeting and talking with Ho Chi Minh is an unforgettable impression. This is a great person, but he never proved himself to be a great person» [1].

3. Noteworthy feature of diplomatic language

Ho Chi Minh has a full convergence of Eastern and Western cultural quintessence, reaching the top of the knowledge of human culture. Especially, he not only mastered many different languages, but also proficiently used them to write newspapers, texts, plays, poems and make diplomatic efforts. Ho Chi Minh is one of the few leaders in the world does not need translators in diplomatic conferences. He was fluent in 6 languages (Chinese, French, English, Russian, German and Thai). Foreign language not only becomes one of the important «tools» to achieve diplomatic goals, but also creates a confident style and diplomatic bravery of Ho Chi Minh. In many interviews of international correspondents, he directly answered in foreign languages. Since then, all the meanings of his nation's struggle have been conveyed to the other nations in the world without any means of translating.

Diplomatic language of Ho Chi Minh is diverse, rich in nuances, emotional, understandable, highly inspiring and persuasive. Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic language shows the natural harmony between national culture and human culture. According to professor Dang Xuan Ky, Ho Chi Minh's language has the humor of French literature, the clarity of Anatole France, the reality of Goethe, the elegant level of Chinese Tang poetry's emotion, the sharpness of Lu Xun. In fact, in communication Ho Chi Minh often cited the Eastern philosophical sentences, especially Confucius's sentences. He always thinks that «words must be simple, clear and practical» [8, p. 191]. He teaches cadres: Words cost nothing, how to say simply and understandably so as to please the listeners, [9, p. 460]. In diplomacy and in the communication with international friends, Ho Chi Minh practiced this smoothly.

In diplomacy, Ho Chi Minh sometimes used style of logical and close reasoning. He used sharp words and persuasive language which were based on the principle of homogeneity, he skillfully added the cultural type of dialogue to diplomacy. He expressed: «although East and West are inherently different, they are not isolated, separated from each other, they all share the view that what you do not want, do not do for others». Thanks to a logical view and strict deduction based on certain premises, Ho Chi Minh forced the opponent not to give a rebuttal. For journalists, especially Western journalists, what convinced them almost was the sharp, concise, deep but clever style of Ho Chi Minh's reasoning and Ho Chi Minh's sincere attitude. The French journalist J. Lakouture said: «President Ho Chi Minh has the ability to conquer his interlocutor from his second sentence» [14, p. 109].

In diplomatic negotiations Ho Chi Minh advocated doing the easy tasks first and doing the hard tasks then, gradually decreasing the scopes of the negotiations, gradually reducing the disagreement in order to reach a «balance» of interest. He upholds the position of building trust with countries. Accord-

ing to Ho Chi Minh, trust and sincerity played an important role in helping relationships between the parties overcome all obstacles: «Only trust each other and equal, honest cooperation, then come a friendly result between the two countries». This characteristic contributes to the world, humanity, and modernity of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture: «Without foreign language skills, it is impossible to mention so-called world and modernity of culture».

4. Noteworthy feature in diplomatic behavior

Ho Chi Minh diplomatic conduct is cultural conduct which includes cultural values. His diplomatic conduct is both natural and fine, brings a message about peace, reaches «artistic range, almost perfection». Since Ho Chi Minh was well-versed in multifaceted culture, so he formed a multidimensional diplomatic conduct, which is both delicate and civilized. There is a harmonious, subtle combination of the poet's soul, the essence of the Eastern sage and the elegant manner of the modern West. Helene Tourmaire said that Ho Chi Minh's image was complete «with the combination of Buddha's wisdom, God's charity, Marxist philosophy, Lenin's revolutionary genius and the affection of a national president, all combined in a very natural manner» [6, p. 92]. Behavior of Ho Chi Minh's diplomacy is delicate, sincere, intelligent, soft and flexible. Uncle Ho was always skillful and tactful, avoiding offending others. Be gentle, polite but not deceiving. In the minds of many people, Ho Chi Minh was a «soft, patient, peaceful person who always sought a reconciliation of the transformative form, unforgiving in principle» [6, p. 119]. He is seeking a skillful harmonious manner, minimizing the cultural impact in diplomatic contact that affects relationships.

The deep understanding of other ethnic cultures, the feeling of the beauty and the respect for the differences makes Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic behavior natural, close and intimate. This is one of the reasons for the charm and attraction of diplomat Ho Chi Minh. The delicate, sincere diplomatic behavior is the anchor point of Ho Chi Minh's

heart, the value that makes Ho Chi Minh different from all other politicians and diplomats. Because of subtlety, Ho Chi Minh captured the psychology of other people, analyzed their strengths and weaknesses, understood them and chose appropriate behaviors to suit each subject in each specific situation. Ho Chi Minh showed clever diplomatic behavior on many subject, many different relationships, such as dealing with countries, behaving at the negotiating, dealing with politicians, with people of countries ... Ho Chi Minh showed his smart behavior when there is a disagreement between the two countries Soviet Union - China, Vietnam got into the middle position. However, Ho Chi Minh still showed a great and unique culture of behavior so that it does not displease either Communist Party; moreover, he also made an important contribution to the Soviet-Chinese diplomatic relations. American historian John Prados remarked: «There is at least one Soviet-Chinese cooperation in this world, that is Vietnam» [11, p. 22].

Flexibility, dexterity, strength, determination and tolerance are the noteworthy features of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic conduct. Ho Chi Minh's tolerance manifests in respecting the difference, unlike himself, but being equal to him, knowing generosity, sympathy, forgiveness, tolerance for all subjects including enemies. Ho Chi Minh built the principle of freedom, equality, respect for morality and righteousness, does not accept unscrupulous compromise with injustices, acts of denying human happiness. That tolerance is not the humility of the weak to the strong, the gift of the strong to the weaker. Ho Chi Minh followed the flow of national diplomacy, raising it into a consistent message throughout his entire diplomatic career. Professor Song Thanh said: «Ho Chi Minh is a symbol, the quintessence of the spirit of tolerance and kindness in Vietnam. Merciful and kindness Ho Chi Minh has been considered a symbol of peaceful culture in this age» [13, p. 93].

5. *The principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» and the art*

of «mindfulness»- The most noteworthy feature in Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture

Ho Chi Minh's principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» is a close combination of traditional diplomatic knowledge that is consistent in principle, flexible in strategy and Marxist materialist dialectic, the art of the war... This combination brings science, practice and right in Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture. Together with dialectical materialist worldview, Ho Chi Minh used the principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» to successfully solve the national diplomacy practices. Ho Chi Minh conceived: «Even though our principles must be firm, our strategies are flexible» [9, p. 555]. Meaningfully, the basic goal, long-term is unchanged, but specific goals, immediate goals can be variables. Multivariable but necessarily revolving around the basic and long-term value axis. The way of expressing is to select the priority, the level of the need to be flexible depending on the correlation of domestic forces and international circumstances, firmly grasping the opportunity to turn the force into a force. The principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» is applied smoothly by Ho Chi Minh in diplomacy.

Ho Chi Minh imbued with the folk philosophy that «people are often influenced by circumstances», in diplomacy he was commonly flexible, willing and ready to do any task for gaining benefits of his national interest. Ho Chi Minh emphasized method of diplomacy positive accept negative, hard blended with soft, get soft won hard. This method is not only theoretical, but also close to the practical of Vietnam. Ho Chi Minh consistent but not weak, flexible but not prone, losing his stance. In diplomacy, a multitude and complex relationships had to be dealt with, Ho Chi Minh saw what to do and how to avoid the highest disadvantages. Mastering the noteworthy of each relationship, Ho Chi Minh correctly handled, promoted and expanded the advantages. He knew how to use the conversation instead of confrontation, how to soothe disagreement, how to avoid face-to-face confrontation in

order to minimize the opponent's attacks, make them less aggressive and disable them. Ho Chi Minh said: «When stones crashed in collision, the two eggs smashed when crushed together. It should one hard hit one soft, so one can be kept» [8, p. 69-70]. The principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» was also introduced by Ho Chi Minh to resolve disputes. V.I. Lenin said: «It is impossible to swear that there will be no compromise. Because of the circumstances required, at times even the most revolutionary Communist Party of the most revolutionary class would need to practice compromise» [2, p. 336]. Ho Chi Minh knew the concessions and stopped at the right time to protect the national interests and preserve the nation. The Ho Chi Minh concession is made in the spirit of principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics» which is a manifestation of the flexible revolutionary struggle method.

Along with the clever application of the principle of «firm in objectives, flexible in strategies and tactics», Ho Chi Minh also promoted the diplomatic art of «mindfulness». The art of «mindfulness» is the essence of national diplomacy that Ho Chi Minh had continued and developed in the new period. Ho Chi Minh's «mindfulness» art is the diplomacy that uses justice and common values that have been recognized by mankind to gain advantage over opponents, to enlist the support and assistance of the world in the struggle for liberation in Vietnam. In order to carry out «mindfulness» diplomacy, Ho Chi Minh used the advantages of Vietnam on the one hand, and on the other hand sought to evoke the revolutionary spirit and national conscience of other countries. He focused on exploiting the good values of these nations such as the spirit of loving freedom, equality and charity. Therefore, in the struggle for liberation, the Vietnamese people have always received the strong support of the people in the socialist countries, Asia, Africa, Latin America and of peace-loving forces around the world, including those who have invaded themselves.

Awakening the conscience is recognized as the self-discipline and the art of «mindfulness» of Ho Chi Minh. Apden Malech Khalin acknowledged: «If Vietnam is the awakening of the conscience of our time, then Uncle Ho Chi Minh is the creator of that conscience» [7, p. 105]. «Mindfulness» diplomacy Ho Chi Minh is not simply a diplomatic method but a diplomatic art - The art of conquering people.

6. Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture - the «torch lead the road» for strengthening Vietnam - Russia comprehensive strategic partnership

Since Vietnamese imbued with Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic culture as well as his love, respect, and love for his brother Soviet union (the present Russian Federation), for many years, Vietnam have consistently considered Russia one of the top priorities in foreign policy. The two countries established diplomatic relations in 1950, became a strategic partner in 2001 and upgraded relationship to a comprehensive strategic partnership in 2012. The people of the two countries are practically celebrating 70 years of the diplomatic relation Russian - Vietnam. Accordingly, the fields of cooperation have been increasingly expanded, which has strengthened and deepened in terms of politics, defense - security, science - technology, education - training, culture and tourism, especially in the field of economy and trade with encouraging results.

Regarding trade cooperation, since the Trade Agreement between Vietnam and the Eurasian Economic Union (VN - EAEU FTA) was signed in 2015 and came into force in 2016, the growth of trade turnover between Vietnam and Russia has made strong progress with an average increase of about 30% / year. Based on statistics of the General Department of Vietnam Customs, the two-way trade turnover between Vietnam and Russia in the first 7 months of 2018 had the highest growth rate since 2012, reaching US \$ 2.67 billion, up 34.2% over the same period in 2017. Vietnam's exports to the Russian market reached US \$ 1.47 billion (up 21%) and imports of Russian goods reached US \$ 1.2 billion (up 55%). As

of July 2018, Russia was Vietnam's 24th largest commodity export market, and the 15th largest importer of Vietnam. As a result, in 2018, Vietnam - Russia back & forth trade turnover increased by 28.63% compared to 2017. In 2019, import and export turnover between the two countries also had a strong increase. In January 2019, Vietnam's export turnover to Russia reached US \$ 230 million, up 29% over the same period last year. Among Vietnamese exports to the Russian market, there are some items with impressive growth, such as textiles, footwear, computers, electronics and components, seafood, cashew nuts, coffee and etc.

About import, the number of goods which Vietnamese companies imported from Russia reached nearly US \$ 193 million, up 23.4% compared to January 2018. Vietnam mainly increased imports of raw materials that Russia has strengths such as iron, steel, seafood, coal, wood and fertilizer. In January 2019, Vietnam's seafood imports from Russia increased by nearly 30%. The items with strong growth such as iron and steel reached US \$ 49 million (up nearly 230% over the same period last year), coal reached US \$ 24 million (up 84%)... Thus, the total trade turnover the back & forth between Vietnam and Russia in January 2019 reached 422.6 million USD, an increase of nearly 27% over the same period in 2018

Regarding investment, in 2018, Russia ranked 24th out of 129 countries and territories investing in Vietnam, there were 123 projects and a total registered capital of 932 million USD. In the opposite direction, Vietnam has also had 22 investment projects in Russia with a total of new and increased capital of nearly US \$ 3 billion. Dairy projects and processing worth more than USD 2 billion invested by TH True Milk Company

in Moscow and Kaluga have become a highlight in Vietnam-Russia investment relations [16].

Energy is also a traditional, effective and strategic area of cooperation, generating significant revenue for Vietnam and Russia budgets. In addition to continuing cooperation within the framework of Vietsovpetro Joint Venture Enterprise by 2030, the two countries have established Rusvietpetro, Vietgazprom, Gazpromviet Joint Ventures to expand oil and gas cooperation in Vietnam, Russia and third countries. The two sides signed and ratified the Agreement and Protocol on cooperation in the oil and gas sector under the Rusvietpetro and Vietsovpetro joint ventures to create conditions for these joint ventures to continue to operate effectively in the coming time.

In order to promote and strengthen the comprehensive strategic partnership between Vietnam and the Russian Federation to be more strongly developed in the coming time, it is necessary to focus on two ways.

Firstly, strengthening cooperation in the field of trade to increase two-way import and export turnover. Efforts are required from state agencies and businesses of the two countries, as well as agencies of the Eurasian Economic Commission.

Secondly, further strengthen cooperation in the field of investment, including Vietnam's investment in Russia and Russia's in Vietnam. To promote cooperation, it is necessary to redefine the investment priorities of the two sides. The authorities of Vietnam, especially the Vietnamese agencies in Russia, need to survey and provide information to investors of the two sides in order to choose the right investment direction. Domestic agencies should take measures to support Russian investors so that they can quickly access Vietnam market.

REFERENCES

1. People's Army Newspaper. November 15, 1969.
2. Duy T. President Ho Chi Minh, the thinker and the great man of culture. Social Sciences Publishing. Hanoi, 1990.
3. Duong.T, Huong N.T.M President Ho Chi Minh with international politicians. News Agency Publishing. Hanoi, 2007.

4. Communist Party of Vietnam. Communist Party of Vietnam Document. Full Episode. Volume 8. National Political Publishing House. Hanoi, 2000.
5. Khoan N.V. Tolerance Ho Chi Minh. Lao Dong Publishing. Hanoi, 1995.
6. Linh D.H, Diep P.H Ho Chi Minh in the memory of international friends. National Political Publishing House. Hanoi, 2009.
7. Loc V.V. President Ho Chi Minh's Aspiration for Peace and National Independence through a number of letters and articles to US Presidents. National Political Publishing, Hanoi, 2016.
8. Minh H.C. Ho Chi Minh: Full Episode. Vol. 5. National Political Publishing. Hanoi, 2011.
9. Minh H.C. Ho Chi Minh: Full Episode. Vol. 8. National Political Publishing, Hanoi, 2011.
10. Minh H.C. Ho Chi Minh: Full Episode. Vol. 15. National Political Publishing. Hanoi, 2011.
11. John Prados The arterial road named Ho Chi Minh in the Vietnam War. Journal of Past and Present, 2005.
12. Thanh Q.D Cultural diplomacy, the third pillar of Vietnam's comprehensive diplomatic strategy. Journal of International Studies, No. 4. 2011.
13. Thanh S. Ho Chi Minh - Brilliant thinker. Publisher of Political Theory. Hanoi, 2005.
14. Thanh S. Ho Chi Minh - Great man of culture. National Political Publishing. Hanoi, 2015.
15. Thuy H.D «Ho Chi Minh Diplomatic Culture and its application in the context of international cooperation in Vietnam today». PhD dissertation of Ho Chi Minh studies. Ho Chi Minh National Academy of Politics. Hanoi, 2019.
16. Happy signals early cross Vietnam - the Russian Federation. URL: <http://www.nhandan.org.vn/kinhte/item/39343202-tin-hieu-vui-dau-nam-cheo-viet-nam-lb-nga.html>

Поступила в редакцию 16.04.2020.

Принята к публикации 19.04.2020.

Для цитирования:

Do Ngoc Hanh Features of Ho Chi Minh's diplomatic style and strengthen Vietnam – Russia comprehensive strategic partnership // Гуманитарный научный вестник. 2020. №3. С. 43-50. URL: <http://naukavestnik.ru/doc/2020/03/DoNgocHanh.pdf>